

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF BIRD IMPACT CHARACTERISTICS OF GLASS FIBER LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

At present, fiber reinforced composites are one of the most common materials in aerospace and aeronautic industries. Its excellent ratios of stiffness to weight and strength to weight make this type of materials to be one of the best choices to aerospace industry structure parts. However, composite structures are often subjected to various impact loads during service, which will produce visually invisible damage in the laminates and result in a significant drop in the load carrying capacity and service life of the structure. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the impact resistance of composite structures and predict the corresponding impact damage characteristics. Therefore, this paper mainly uses the finite element analysis software Ls-dyna to establish a finite element model of glass fiber laminates subjected to bird impact, and simulates the high-velocity impact response of the bird's body. Using the initial velocity and the incident angle as variables, the pressure generated during the impact process, the delamination damage area, the kinetic energy of the bird body, and the residual velocity as the research objects. The results show that at different initial velocities, the energy absorbed by the laminate and the initial velocity of the bird are approximately linear. When the initial velocity is less than the penetration limit velocity, the peak value of the impact force increases as the velocity increases, but after the velocity is greater than the penetration limit velocity, the impact force decreases immediately after reaching the peak force. At the same initial velocity, the peak force of the impact force increases with the increase of the incident angle, and the delamination damage area also increases.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are widely used in the aerospace industry due to their small specific gravity, large specific strength and specific modulus, good designability, high fatigue resistance and vibration damping. It is believed that the amount of advanced composite materials used in aircraft is a sign of advanced nature. At the same time, the number of aircraft accidents has increased year by year. The bird collision has been one of the three major disasters that have plagued the safety of air transportation since the invention was invented. The aircraft may suffer from the impact of birds during flight or take-off and landing. When the aircraft body is subjected to bird impact, it will affect the normal flight of the aircraft, and may cause flight accidents. One of the measures to reduce the occurrence of such accidents is to study the mechanism of bird impact on composite laminates and their members from the theoretical and experimental aspects, to calculate and analyze the structure, strength and performance of composite

laminates, to guide engineering design, and to improve the ability of composite members to resist bird impact damage.

Statistics from the FAA on the collision of American civil aircraft birds indicate that bird strike hazards are increasing year by year. The most common impact positions are wing leading edge, nose, engine and windshield, as shown in the Figure 1. In order to reduce the harm caused by bird collision, many scholars have studied it.

Figure 1: Common bird impact locations

Hedayati R[1] strike the part of the plane with the bird's head, tail, bottom and wings, respectively. It was found that the impact of the bottom impact of the birds was the most destructive, while the tail impact was less dangerous, and the peak pressure of the bottom side impact was about three times that of the tail side. The shape of the sphere, the cylinder, the hemispherical cylinder and the ellipsoidal geometry are used to simulate the bird collision, it was found that the hemispherical cylinder showed the best effect for the case of the tail impact, and the ellipsoid may be the best candidate for the bird substitution model for the bottom impact.

Because the true bird body is composed of bones, blood, meat, etc., and different birds are different, the experimental repeatability is poor, so most scholars use gelatine simulation bird bombs with 10% gap to carry out experiments. In the study of Lavoie MA [2], the preparation methods and materials of gelatine artificial birds are given, as shown in Table 1. The impact pressure was obtained by theory, Experiments and finite element method. It was found that the agreement was good within a certain error range.

Ingredient
– 1000 g cold water.
– 100 g ballisitic gelatine powder.
– 25 g sodium carboxymethylcellulose.
– 6 g aluminum acetate basic.
– 4 drops of cinnamomum zeylanium.
Procedure
1. Mix the cold water and gelatine, wait for 5 min.
2. Heat up the gelatine mix to 45_C.
3. Meanwhile, weigh the aluminum acetate basic and sodium carboxymethylcellulose and mix them together.
4. Weigh 1050 g of the gelatine mix and pour into the blender.
5. Add 4 drops of cinnamomum zeylanium.
6. Start the blender.
7. Open the lid and add the aluminum acetate basic and sodium carboxymethylcellulose.
8. Close the lid and let spin at the lowest velocity for 3–5 s.
9. Stop the blender, pour into the mould and cool in the refrigerator.

Table 1: Gelatine's preparation procedure.

The bird body material models commonly used in the finite element simulation study of bird impact include the elastoplastic material model with failure, the isotropic elastoplastic fluid dynamics model and the hydrodynamic model described by the equation of state equation (EOS). In the study of Liu J [3], it is shown that the elastoplastic material model with failure is most suitable for bird strike simulation under low velocity impact, the isotropic elastoplastic fluid dynamics solid model is most suitable for bird strike simulation under medium velocity impact, and the hydrodynamic model described by the equation of state (EOS) is most suitable for bird strike simulation under high velocity impact. Reza [4] used numerical calculations and experimental methods to discuss the effects of different bird shapes on the impact and determined the shape of the bird close to the experimental data. Allaey F[5] revealed some key parameters affecting impact state by taking peak pressure as the research object through simulation and experiment. The results showed that the bird impact process could be divided into impact state and stable state, with higher impact pressure and lower stable pressure, and the tilt of the target plate has a great influence on the impact pressure. J.P.Hou [6] conducted a bird strike test on composite flat blades and performed Non Destructive testing on the specimen after impact. The results show that the delamination damage is mainly determined by the toughness of the resin, and the failure of the fiber is mainly determined by the strength of the fiber. The combination of high strength fiber and high toughness resin has the strongest impact resistance, and the high strength fiber and low toughness resin are relatively poor.

In this paper, the dynamic response of composite laminates under high-velocity impact loads of birds is used. The Ls-dyna dynamic analysis module is used to analyze the large deformation problem of birds impact composite laminates by the coupling of SPH particles and finite element contact surfaces. Taking the initial velocity and incident angle of the bird as variables, the dynamic response of the bird's impact characteristics of the laminate, the failure mode of the laminate and the delamination damage area were analyzed. Finally, the inter-layer failure is mainly layering.

2 MODEL DESCRIPTION

2.1 Composite model

Composite laminates exhibit complex failure modes and become difficult to test when they fail [7]. Generally speaking, there are mainly two types of failure, in-layer failure and interlayer failure. In-layer failure includes fiber tensile failure, fiber compression failure, matrix tensile failure and matrix compression damage, and interlayer damage is mainly layering.

Composite failure criteria are mainly divided into three categories: The first category is a criterion that can only determine whether failure has occurred, such as the maximum stress criterion, the maximum strain criterion, the Tsai-Hill criterion, and the Tsai-Wu tensor criterion. The second category is criteria that can determine not only whether a failure has occurred but also what kind of failure has occurred. Such as Hashin criteria, Puck guidelines and Chang-Chang criteria, etc. The third category is the Christensen criterion based on the mesoscopic model. The most widely used criteria for Chang-Chang can be expressed as follows:

For the tensile fiber mode:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_t}\right)^2 + \beta \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

For the compressive fiber mode:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_c}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (2)$$

For the tensile matrix mode:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (3)$$

For the compressive matrix mode:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{2S}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_c}{2S}\right)^2 - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_2}{Y_c} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

In the above formula, σ_1, σ_2 represents the stress in the first and second principal directions of the material, X_t is longitudinal tensile strength, X_c is longitudinal compression strength, Y_t is transverse tensile strength, Y_c is transverse compressive strength, S is Shear strength, β is Nonlinear shear stress parameter.

Lamination damage of composite materials has accounted for 45% of the damage of composite materials, and even accounts for 60%-70% in the case of low-velocity impact. Therefore, it is very necessary to conduct depth research. In recent years, cohesive element and cohesive contact have been widely used in finite element problems to simulate composite delamination damage. Numerous studies have shown that delamination of composite materials generally occurs between two layers with different ply angles. Therefore, the numerical simulation of layered damage based on cohesion element is to establish a layer of cohesive element between two layers with different layering angles, and to set binding contact between the upper and lower layers, so that the displacement and stress between the interfaces are continuous, as shown in Figure 2. As the damage of the bonding layer increases, macroscopic cracks are generated, which eventually manifests as delamination. The method based on cohesive force contact is to set a certain strength on the contact surface between the two layers, and when the failure criterion is satisfied, the contact fails and delamination occurs.

Figure 2: Cohesion constitutive relation

2.2 Bird model

The simulated bird bombs used in international practice mainly have three shapes: standard cylinder shape, intermediate cylinder shape at both ends of hemispheres, ellipsoidal shape, and their length diameter ratio (L/D) is 2, as shown in Figure 3. The quality is 2bl, 4bl and 6bl respectively.

Figure 3: Simulation bird geometry model

In this paper, the central cylindrical shape of the two hemispheres is used to simulate the bird body, and the Plastic Kinematic model is used by the bird. the yield condition is expressed as:

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{2} \xi_{ij} \xi_{ij} - \frac{\sigma_y^2}{3} = 0 \quad (5)$$

In the middle

$$\xi_{ij} = S_{ij} - \alpha_{ij} \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha_{ij}^v = \frac{2}{3} (1 - \beta) E_p \varepsilon_{eff}^p \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha_{ij}^{\nabla} = \frac{2}{3}(1 - \beta)E_p \dot{\epsilon}_{eff}^p \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_{ij}^{n+1} = \alpha_{ij}^n + \left(\alpha_{ij}^{\nabla n+\frac{1}{2}} + \alpha_{ik}^n \Omega_{ij}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} + \alpha_{ij}^n \Omega_{jk}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \right) \Delta t^{n+\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

P and C is User input parameter, E_p is the plastic hardening modulus, $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate, E_{eff}^p is the equivalent plastic strain.

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \sqrt{\epsilon_{ij}\epsilon_{ij}} \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_{eff}^p = \int_0^t \left(\frac{2}{3} \dot{\epsilon}_{eff}^p \dot{\epsilon}_{eff}^p \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (11)$$

The failure criterion of the material model is strain failure, that is

$$\epsilon \geq [\epsilon] \quad (12)$$

2.3 Finite element model and material parameters

The finite element software Ls-dyna is used to simulate the impact process. Since impact damage not only includes the damage of matrix and fiber, but also includes layered damage, chang-chang criterion was introduced as the damage criterion of fiber and matrix, and viscous contact simulation was set between layers. The glass fiber material parameters are shown in table 1. The total thickness of the laminate is 5mm, laminates with the stacking sequence of [0/90/0/90/0], each layer has a thickness of 1mm, and the grid is divided by 8-node solid elements.

ρ ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)
1500	34.69	9.51	9.51	14.02
G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
9.51	9.51	0.291	0.291	0.07
X^T (MPa)	X^C (MPa)	Y^T (MPa)	Y^C (MPa)	S^L (MPa)
1098	892	39	185	39

Table 2: Material properties of laminate

During high-velocity impact, the bird is observed to be highly distorted and crushed, acting like a fluid. It is difficult to simulate this behavior using traditional finite element models of Lagrangian meshes. Mesh distortion can lead to unstable or even non-converged calculations, while Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) is a meshless method. The basic idea of this method is to describe continuous fluid (or solid) as interacting particle, and its self-adaptability can naturally deal with large deformation problems in impact. Therefore, the bird body is modeled by SPH particles, the material used a plastic kinematic model with strain failure. The material parameters are shown in Table 2. The SPH particles are placed in contact with each layer with ERODING_NODES_TO_SURFACE. The SPH particles are set to Slave nodes, the laminate unit set to the Master surface, and the AUTOMATIC_ONE_WAY_SURFACE_TO_SURFACE_TIEBREAK contact is set between the layers, and fixed boundary conditions are set around. The finite element model is shown in Figure 4

Mass density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Young's modulu (GPa)	Poisson's ratio
950	10	0.3
Yield stress (MPa)	Tangent modulus (MPa)	Failure strain
1	5	1.25

Table 2: Material properties of laminate

Figure 4: Finite element model

3. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF BIRD IMPACT LAMINATE

3.1 Influence of impact velocity

The weight is 4lb, and the geometric model is center cylinder is and hemispherical on both sides, $D=113.2\text{mm}$, $L=226.4\text{mm}$, Vertically (90°) impact laminates at velocity of 100, 120, 140, 160, and 180 m/s, Figure 5 shows the relationship between initial impact velocity and residual velocity. The negative velocity represents that the bird's unpenetrated laminate is rebounded. From the figure, the penetration limit velocity is about 140 m/s.

Figure 5: Initial velocity and residual velocity

Figure 6 is a plot of the impact force history during the impact process, It is shown that before the critical penetration velocity, the impact force increases with the increase of the velocity, Increase velocity by 20m/s, increase impact pressure by 70kN ,and after reaching the peak, it shows a relatively slow decline process. The maximum impact pressure at critical velocity is 313KnN. When the velocity exceeds the critical velocity, it shows a momentary decline after reaching the peak. Corresponding to the fracture of the material in the laminate, the load capacity is reduced.

Figure 7 shows the relationship between the kinetic energy loss and the impact velocity of the bird. The energy lost by the bird body can also be considered as the energy absorbed by the laminate during the impact. The figure shows that the energy lost by the bird body and the impact velocity are approximately linear. The impact velocity increases and increases. The energy lost is mainly used for the fracture of the fiber and the matrix, as well as the interlayer delamination.

Figure 6: Impact pressure history curve at different velocity

Figure 7: the kinetic energy loss of the bird body and the initial velocity

3.2 Influence of incident angle

In this section, the same simulated bird bombs as in the previous section are used, and at an initial velocity of 140 m/s, the laminates are struck at an incident angle of 30°, 60° and 90°, respectively, as shown in Figure 8. The parameters of the laminate are identical to those in Section 3.1.

Figure 8: Bird impact diagram

Figure 9 shows the force time history curve during the impact. Compared with the normal incidence, the peak pressure of 60° incident decreases by 15.8%, and the pressure peak of 30° decreases by 48.9%. It indicates that the inclination of the target has a great influence on the peak value of the impact pressure. Figure 10 shows the relationship between the layered area and the incident angle. As can be seen from the figure, the delamination area increases with the increase of the incident angle. The reason is that the large incident angle causes a large impact force, the inter-layer force is also increased, eventually leading to interlayer delamination.

Figure 9: Impact pressure history curve at different incidence angle

Figure 10: delamination area at different incidence angle

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, the numerical simulation method is used to analyze the bird's glass fiber laminates, and the effects of initial velocity and incident angle on the impact characteristics of birds are studied. The penetration limit velocity of the bird striking laminate is obtained, compare the peak pressure during the impact and the final delamination damage area. The results show: 1) In the case of normal incidence, the penetration velocity of the laminate is about 140m/s. When the initial velocity of the bird is less than or equal to the critical velocity of penetration, the peak of the impact increases with the increase of the initial velocity, maximum pressure reaches 313Kn. When the velocity exceeds the critical velocity, the impact force is sharply small after reaching the peak. 2) Compared with the normal incidence, the peak pressure of 60° incident decreases by 15.8%, and the pressure peak of 30° decreases by 48.9%. at the same time, The delamination damage area is reduced by 24% and 65.5 respectively.

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